

THE EFFECTS OF DEFORMING KNITTED GLASS PREFORMS ON THE TENSILE PROPERTIES OF RESULTANT COMPOSITE LAMINATES

K. H. Leong¹, M. Nguyen² & I. Herszberg²

¹*Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Ltd. (CRC-ACS),
506 Lorimer Street, Fishermens Bend, VIC 3207, AUSTRALIA.*

²*The Sir Lawrence Wackett Centre for Aerospace Design and Technology, RMIT,
GPO Box 2476V, Melbourne, VIC 3001, AUSTRALIA.*

SUMMARY: The effects of deforming knitted fabrics on the tensile properties of their resultant composites have been evaluated. The properties were studied for both the course and wale directions for composite laminates with fabrics that had been deformed in either of the two directions. It was found that as the amount of deformation in the fabrics was increased tensile stiffness and strength of the laminates improved markedly in the direction which the knitted fabrics had been deformed. When the laminates were loaded normal to the direction in which the fabric had been deformed, it was found that deformation in the wale and course directions resulted in improvement and deterioration of tensile properties, respectively. The relative orientation of the fracture planes with respect to the loading axis was also found to be dependent on the degree of deformation that had been induced in the knitted fabric.

KEYWORDS: knitted preforms, textile composites, tensile properties, deformation, fracture mechanisms

INTRODUCTION

The use of knitting technology with advanced fibres, such as glass, carbon and aramid, to produce near-net-shape fabrics, or "socks", has in recent years received increasing interest from the composite materials community. In conjunction with a suitable liquid moulding technique, such as Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM), the fabrics have the potential to be used for production of a wide variety of composite structures with complex shapes [1,2]. Whilst such fabrics are obviously advantageous in terms of reducing production cost as a result of minimum material wastage and reduced labour time, the development of a suitable "sock" for a particular structure is often a time consuming, and hence an expensive task. Therefore, unless such costs are justified, an alternative cheaper method would be to impregnate flat knitted fabrics in a forming tool to obtain the required shape of the component [3].

During the process of forming a flat knitted fabric (*e.g.* during deep drawing), it is inevitable that the fabric would be deformed due to stretching so that optimum conformibility to the shape of the component is achieved. The highly looped fibre architecture of the knitted fabric easily affords such deformation, and hence its excellent forming characteristics. However, the exercise results in distortion to the knit structure which could result in tearing and/or isolated

bunching of the fabric [3]. The distortion would also cause a degree of fibre orientation in the direction of stretching which, in turn, would affect the mechanical properties of the resultant composite [4,5]. In addition, previous investigations carried out on composite materials manufactured from knitted glass and carbon fabrics have revealed that the mechanical properties of knitted composites are anisotropic [4,6-9], and they are dependent on factors such as the number of layers of fabric [4,5,10], stitch density (which is a measure of the tightness of the knit) [7], knit architecture [8] and fibre volume fraction [9-11].

Whilst knitted composites generally have inferior in-plane strength and stiffness compared with materials such as woven composites, they are superior in terms of impact resistance and retention of post-impact properties [12], with comparable bearing capabilities [9,12]. Consequently, these positive attributes partly account for the increasing effort to develop this technology for niche applications [13,14].

In the present study, the effects of deformation of knitted fabrics on the tensile properties of resultant composites have been investigated for the weft knitted Milano rib fibre architecture. The properties were investigated for both the course and wale directions for composites with fabrics deformed in either of the two directions. This study was also supported by fractographic studies using stereoptical microscopy. It is noteworthy that the research reported in this paper is an auxiliary part of a larger project that is currently undertaken at the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Ltd. (CRC-ACS). The project involves the development of a more cost-effective technique for producing a non-structural helicopter component which is currently being manufactured using the tape layup method [3].

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Manufacture

The test panels used in this experimental programme were manufactured via RTM and using up to 7 layers of weft knitted Milano rib fabric (see Figure 1 for loop structure) and Derakane 411-C50 vinyl ester resin/Triganox T-239 catalyst/CoNap promoter/2, 4-P inhibitor. A 10-gauge, flat bed knitting machine was employed to produce a fabric of nominal areal weight of 730g m^{-1} (undeformed) using $2 \times 68\text{tex}$ multi-filament glass fibre.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of the Milano rib structure.

A rig, details of which are given elsewhere [15], was developed and built to afford systematic deformation to the knitted fabrics. In the course direction, the fabrics were deformed to 20%, 35% and 45% (maximum achievable) while in the wale direction to 20%, 30% and 40% (maximum achievable). Undeformed (0%) fabrics were also considered.

The fibre volume fractions (V_f) of the laminates were maintained fairly constant at approximately 55% by varying the number of knitted fabric layers to isolate the effect of V_f on strength. Further, a reasonably uniform resin flow pattern and, hence, quality in terms of porosity and wetting, between the different laminates could also be maintained. Hence, between 6 and 7 fabric layers were used to produce the laminates. It is noteworthy that earlier studies [9,14] have established the relative insensitivity of tensile strength and stiffness of the Milano rib structure to the number of fabric layers used in a composite; what is in fact more important is the fibre volume fraction.

Coupon Tests

Straight-sided tensile test specimens of 3mm × 25mm × 210mm nominal dimensions were used throughout the programme. Tensile tests were conducted using an Instron 50kN screw-driven mechanical testing machine under displacement control at a nominal rate of 0.5mm min⁻¹. A gauge length of 120mm was used leaving 45mm on each end of the specimens which were gripped in the testing machine. An open weave emery cloth (Screenbak™) was used instead of tabs in the gripped areas of the specimens and this appeared to be effective in promoting failure to occur within the gauge length of the specimens. Specimens of both deformed and undeformed fabrics were tested in the wale and course directions. No less than 5 specimens were considered for each case.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Introduction

To facilitate the presentation of the results, discussion and conclusions, the following abbreviations are used in the rest of this paper.

- δWW = deformed and tested in the wale direction;
- δCC = deformed and tested in the course direction;
- δWC = deformed in the wale direction and tested in the course direction; and
- δCW = deformed in the course direction and tested in the wale direction;

where δ represents the amount of deformation.

Stress-Strain Behaviour

Figure 2 shows a typical stress-strain curve for the 45CW laminate. It reveals that the laminate initially exhibited linear behaviour but then transformed to pseudo-plastic in the latter stages of loading before a maximum stress (defined as the tensile strength) was reached, after which a rather gradual reduction ensued. The transition in linear to non-linear behaviour generally corresponded to the onset of matrix cracking. The stress-strain behaviour described above was generally observed to be similar for all the specimens, irrespective of the direction and degree of fabric deformation or the relative loading axis of the laminates.

Fig. 2: Typical stress-strain curve of the knitted composite under study.

Tensile Strength and Stiffness

The fibre content of the different laminates varied between 52% and 57% and therefore, to afford comparison, the experimental results of each set of laminates have been normalised to a constant V_f of 55% and presented in Figures 3 and 4 for strength and stiffness, respectively.

From Figures 3 and 4, it will be noted that when the fabrics had not been deformed, the resultant composite laminates displayed higher strength and stiffness in the wale than in the course direction. Although no systematic measurements have been carried out, it is clear from qualitative assessments that the content of fibres oriented in the wale direction is higher, which would account for the better tensile properties along that axis.

As the amount of deformation in the fabrics was increased, the tensile strength and stiffness of the laminates improved markedly in the direction which the fabrics had been deformed. It is interesting to note that this behaviour is consistent with the results of Ha *et al.* [5] for composites derived from deformed and undeformed plain weft knitted carbon fabrics. This improvement in strength and stiffness with the degree of deformation is attributed to an increase in the content of fibres oriented along the loading axis as the knitted fibres were increasingly drawn and straightened in the direction of stretch. The present results also imply that the fibres were not significantly pre-stressed (*i.e.* the yarns were straightened along the stretch axis but not elongated), if at all, when the fabrics were deformed within the levels considered in this study. If the fibres were significantly pre-stressed, then there would be a deterioration in tensile strength with increased fabric deformation which was not observed. In addition, the improvements in tensile properties with increased deformation were revealed to be considerably more pronounced for strength (40WW = 72.4%; 45CC = 89.9%) than they are for stiffness (40WW = 17.5%; 45CC = 38.5%). This is not unexpected since a slight misalignment in fibre orientation from the loading axis (up to $\sim 25^\circ$) is known to have a more significant influence on strength than on stiffness [16].

When loading normal to the direction of stretch, Ha *et al.* [5], on plain weft knitted carbon composite laminates, have shown that tensile properties deteriorated with the degree of

deformation in the knitted fabric. This degradation in tensile properties is believed to be attributed to a reduction in content of fibres oriented in the course direction as the fabric was deformed along the wale, and *vice versa*. This is consistent with the simultaneous increase in the content of fibres oriented in the direction of stretch which accounts for the improved WW and CC properties mentioned earlier.

For the laminates considered in the present work, however, loading normal to the direction of fabric deformation resulted in an improvement and a deterioration in the WC and CW tensile properties, respectively. Inspection of fabrics subjected to various amounts deformation suggests that the opposing trends observed for the WC and CW laminates are due to the manner in which the Milano rib structure changes with deformation in the wale and course directions.

Fig. 3: The influence of deformation of the knitted fabric on composite strength.

Fig. 4: The influence of deformation of the knitted fabric on composite stiffness.

It is clear from Figures 5d and 5e that when the fabric was deformed in the course direction, the individual courses were simply drawn closer together, as would be in a plain weft knit structure, thus effectively reducing the amount of fibres that contribute to the wale-wise properties. Consequently, the tensile properties of the CW laminates deteriorated with the amount of fabric deformation. It is interesting to observe that the "loopy" nature of the knit structure was increasingly diminished with deformation of the fabric in the course direction.

However, as illustrated in Figures 5b and 5c, when the fabric was deformed in the wale direction, the "loopy" nature of the knit structure was retained. The legs of the loops (see Figure 6) not only remained oriented at an angle to the two principal axes, *i.e.* wale and course, so that these fibre components contribute to the tensile properties in both the directions. The enhancement of strength and stiffness of the WC laminates is in fact attributed to the increasing straightening of these fibre components with deformation.

Close examination of Figure 5 further revealed that the fibres are much straighter in the course-deformed fabrics than in the wale-deformed ones, and this is probably the reason for the steeper rate of increase both in strength (WW = 1.81% per unit stretch; CC = 2.00% per unit stretch) as well as in stiffness (WW = 0.43% per unit stretch; CC = 0.86% per unit stretch) for the former compared with the latter laminates.

Fig. 5. The effects of deformation on the effective fibre architecture of the Milano rib fabric.

Fig. 6: Components of a weft knitted loop.

Fracture Mechanisms and Failure Modes

Irrespective of the amount of deformation in the fabric, and the relative loading direction, the first discernible damage in the specimens was observed to be matrix cracking (see Figure 7), which increased in intensity with loading until final failure of the specimen intercepted. It will be noted that this microcracking appeared macroscopically as whitened areas in the specimens. The locations of the microcracks within the gauge section were initially relatively random, but as loading progressed and more microcracks formed, they appeared to coalesce together to form regular rows of matrix cracks that span the whole width of the specimens (see Figure 7). Earlier work by Leong *et al.* [9] have revealed that the microcracks do not actually span the whole thickness of the laminates but are arrested by the complex array of fibres that came about through the intermeshing between the different fabric layers.

They also pointed out that the matrix crack spacings were of the order of the distances between the loop components in the fabric (see Figure 6), depending on the loading axis.

Fig. 7: Typical fractured specimens made from (a) undeformed, and (b & c) deformed, fabrics.

In the present work, ultimate failure is defined as the point at which there was an appreciable drop in the load-carrying capacity of the specimen. In most cases, when this happened, the specimens were not completely broken whereby the matching fracture surfaces was bridged by a ligament of fabric material. It is noteworthy that the gradual drop in stress after reaching a maximum, as depicted by the stress-strain curve in Figure 2, suggests that groups of fibres within the fracture plane had failed sequentially so that if a test were terminated before all the fibres within the plane had failed a ligament of fabric material would remain. Consistent with this fracture behaviour, ultimate failure for the knitted composites was not catastrophic. It is believed that the appreciable drop in the load-carrying capacity, and hence ultimate failure, of the laminates occurred with the onset of gross fibre fracture, *i.e.* breakage of the first fibre bundles.

The amount of deformation that the fabric had undergone was also observed to have an influence on the fracture mode of the resultant composite laminates. By referring to Figure 7, it can be seen that the laminates had failed in one of three modes with respect to the relative orientation of the fracture plane to the loading axis. More precisely, the specimens of undeformed (and lightly deformed) fabric failed in a plane normal to the loading axis (see Figure 7a) whilst the specimens of more heavily deformed fabrics generally failed at an angled plane of approximately 20° to 30° (see Figure 7c). It has been noted that the angles of the fracture planes on the whole increased with the amount of deformation of the fabrics. In some intermediate cases, the specimens failed in a combination of both modes, usually beginning at angle and finishing up normal, to the loading axis (see Figure 7b).

Post-failure examination of the fracture surfaces, using an Olympus ZHS stereoptical microscope, confirmed that ultimate failure of the specimens was indeed dictated by the capacity of the fibres to withstand loading after matrix cracking. As expected the fibre

breakages occurred in a fashion very similar to that observed by Ramakrishna and Hull [10] for their plain weft knitted carbon samples, whereby the fracture plane coincided with the plane of lowest local fibre content. In other words, wale-tested specimens tended to have fibres breaking at the legs of loops, and course-tested ones at the needle/sinker loops. It will be noted that, as in the specimens that failed in a plane normal to the loading axis, fibre breakages in the wale- and course-tested specimens that failed at an angled plane also occurred predominantly at legs of loops and needle/sinker loops, respectively. These latter fibre breakages were however not confined to a single row of wale of course but, instead, they consistently moved to adjacent rows causing large matrix cracks to form along the way.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, the effects of deforming knitted fabrics on the tensile properties of their resultant composites have been evaluated. The properties were studied for both the course and wale directions for composite laminates with fabrics that had been deformed in either of the two directions. It was revealed that as the amount of deformation in the fabrics was increased tensile stiffness and strength of the laminates improved markedly in the direction which the knitted fabrics had been deformed. This improvement in strength and stiffness with the degree of deformation is attributed to an increase in the content of fibres oriented along the loading axis as the knitted fibres were increasingly drawn and straightened in the direction of stretch. When the laminates were loaded normal to the direction in which the fabric had been deformed, it was revealed that deformation in the wale and course directions resulted in improvement and deterioration of tensile properties, respectively. The opposing trends observed for the CW and WC laminates is accounted for by a difference in the nature of distortion to the Milano rib structure when it is deformed in the two principal directions.

The orientation of fracture planes with respect to the loading axis appeared to be also dependent on the degree of deformation that had been induced in the knitted fabric. Specimens of undeformed (and lightly deformed) fabric failed in a plane normal to the loading axis whilst the specimens of more heavily deformed fabrics generally failed at an angled plane of approximately 20° to 30° depending on the amount of fabric deformation. In some intermediate cases, the specimens failed in a combination of both modes, usually beginning at angle and finishing up normal, to the loading axis. Nevertheless, irrespective of the amount of deformation in the fabric, ultimate failure of the wale- and course-tested specimens was attributed to fibre breakages occurring predominantly at the legs of loops and needle/sinker loops, respectively.

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